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Professional Training of Future Librarians at the Vasyl' Stus Donetsk National University

Objective. The purpose of the study is to represent the experience and directions of professional training of future library specialists in a higher education institution, which is based on the integration of education, modern information and communication technologies, and a practical component, which enables the professional realization of specialists in modern library institutions in accordance with the requirements of the information society. **Methods.** The research used a complex of general and special methods of scientific knowledge, namely: the method of document analysis by studying and presenting educational programs for training future specialists regarding their compliance with the needs of the labor market; the method of monitoring the process of training applicants in a higher education institution, its features and adaptation to the requirements of the information society; descriptive method and method of logical presentation of research results. **Results.** The results of the study showed that the organization of professional training, and learning strategies, which are applied at the Vasyl' Stus Donetsk National University at the Department of Management Information Systems, contribute to the successful professional realization of future library specialists in accordance with today's requirements. Graduates of the department are highly qualified and competitive specialists on the labor market. **Conclusions.** The conclusions argue for the relevance of professional training of future specialists in the library field in the context of digital transformations of society. The importance of improving educational programs aimed at training specialists in the library sphere was emphasized.

Keywords: information society; library; librarian; Vasyl' Stus Donetsk National University; professional training

Introduction

Civilizational changes taking place under the influence of informatization, digitization, and the use of artificial intelligence significantly affect all spheres of social life, form the latest social relations, and require the training of highly qualified specialists with the appropriate skills and competencies. Therefore, the education system of Ukraine faces important tasks related to updating the content of the training of future specialists, the organization and technology of the educational process, and ultimately the transformation of the entire education system.

Higher education in Ukraine is being modernized and integrated into the world's educational and scientific space. In 2022, the «Strategy for the Development of Higher Education in Ukraine for 2022-2032» (Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine, 2022) was approved, which defines the directions of the development of the higher education system at the current stage of the development of society and the country's economy, its main characteristics, which must be formed by 2032. Definition of problems that exist in the system of higher education. It is noted that the main content of higher education is determined by the standards of higher education of the new generation, which are based on the competency approach.

Modern conditions require professionals with high professional competence. Today, expertise is defined by the ability to adapt to changes and needs of the labor market, to make decisions quickly, and to learn throughout life. Training a specialist of this level is the main task for higher education.

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In the conditions of the information society, the problem of professional training of future specialists in the information field, in particular library specialists, is relevant, where it is important to focus on the formation of the set of competencies of the future specialist.

Today dictates new requirements for library staff, including the ability to navigate large information flows, analyze and summarize information, think critically, etc.

It is obvious that there are a lot of changes and challenges connected to library work in the networked society. Existing information chains and distribution models are disrupted and individual information practices change. The keys to future professionals seem to be to understand trends and predict consequences. Technological change is at the forefront leading to

- new information behavior (connected, interactive, fragmented)
- new research practices and processes (e-science, scholarly communication)
- new information provision models (new actors, open access, expensive e-publications)
- new digital collections (research data, e-publications)
- new library services (integrated into learning and research)
- new library professional skills that support the above development and change (Widén & Kronqvist-Berg, 2014).

Modern educational and professional programs for training students of higher education in specialty 029 «Information, library and archival affairs» should be aimed at the formation of such competencies.

The purpose of the study is to highlight the experience and directions of professional training of future library specialists in a higher education institution, which is based on the integration of education, modern information and communication technologies, and a practical component, which enables the professional realization of specialists in modern library institutions in accordance with the requirements of the information society.

The problem of professional training of future specialists to work in modern libraries is relevant among scientists, theoreticians, and practitioners of the library sphere. The scientific discourse highlights a complex of issues related to the development of modern forms of the educational process, the introduction of innovative methods, the adaptation of distance learning tools in the educational process, etc. In the scientific publications of N. Bachynska, L. Savenkova, A. Chachko, and others theoretical and methodical principles of professional training of specialists in the library and information field were studied; I. Guziy, Yu. Kozlovskiy, N. Mukan investigate the specifics of professional training of specialists in information, library, and archival affairs based on the application of an integrative approach; S. Chukanova, A. Gumenchuk, O. Bashun, V. Pashkova and others studied general trends, specifics of organizational and content transformations of higher library education in the USA; A. Plakhtiy, V. Zagumenna and others analyzed the professional training of library specialists in the context of the development of electronic government.

Taking into account the fact that in recent years certain changes have taken place in Ukraine regarding the management of higher education, accreditation of educational programs, the content of education in general, we consider it relevant to highlight the experience of training future specialists in the information and library sphere in the context of the further transformation of bachelor's and master's educational programs, their improvement, respectively to the requirements of the digital society.

Methods

The research results were obtained thanks to the application of a complex of general and special methods of scientific knowledge. This is how the method of document analysis was used,

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namely the study and presentation of educational programs according to the training levels of future specialists in the specialty 029 Information, library, and archival affairs at the Vasyl' Stus Donetsk National University, substantiation of their compliance with the needs of the labor market. The method of observing the process of training applicants, in particular observation of lectures, practical classes, practices, and other aspects of the educational process made it possible to reveal its peculiarities and adaptability to modern requirements. The descriptive method and the method of logical presentation of the research results presented the features of the process of training future specialists in the library field in the institution of higher education.

Results and Discussion

The information society is characterized by the fact that information, knowledge, and technologies play a major role in the development of the economy, science, culture, and other spheres of society. We will present several arguments regarding the importance of updating professional training for professional implementation in new conditions:

1. Development of technologies: The information society depends on the development and implementation of the latest technologies. Specialists with a deep understanding of their field can create and improve technologies that contribute to the further development of society.

2. Competitiveness: The requirements of the information society are changing rapidly, and only well-trained specialists will be able to meet these changes. Companies and organizations need qualified specialists who can adapt to new conditions and develop innovative solutions.

3. Ensuring the quality of information: In the information society, it is important to ensure the quality and reliability of information. Professionals can analyze, verify, and interpret information from various sources, which is key to making informed decisions.

4. Creation of new knowledge: Scientific progress is the basis of the development of society. Specialists who have received deep professional training can conduct research and create new knowledge, which contributes to scientific and technological evolution.

5. Development of civic consciousness: Modern specialists also play an important role in the education of civic consciousness, popularization of true information, and rejection of misinformation. This contributes to the preservation of democratic values and the development of civil society.

6. Interdisciplinarity The information society requires cooperation between different fields of knowledge. Specialists with a wide range of knowledge and skills can work more easily in cross-industry environments.

And today, every field of human activity is changing and needs just such specialists.

The socio-cultural sphere in general and libraries, as socio-cultural institutions, under the influence of changes in society, evolve and integrate into the network environment, both the social role of libraries and the role of the library specialist in a modern library are changing. Knowledge, abilities, skills, and target instructions of specialists who are well versed in the latest technologies, capable of producing original ideas, are decisive factors affecting the successful functioning of the institution, the quality of the provided information, and the level of service to readers. It is such a specialist who can implement the concept of intellectualization of the library profession and provide high-quality information and bibliographic service (Plakhtii, 2018).

Transformations of the socio-cultural sphere in general and the development of the potential of libraries directly depend on a professional who creatively and fully uses all professional opportunities. Therefore, the professional training of future specialists for work in

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libraries, who are ready to make modern changes in the library industry, is a task for higher education institutions that train specialists in this field.

We will cite several aspects to justify the importance of updating the professional training of future library specialists in the context of the requirements of the information society:

1. Effective information management. In the modern information environment, the volume and variety of information is growing. Library specialists systematize, store, and provide access to information. They are key figures for effective management of knowledge and resources.

2. Dissemination of true information. In conditions of wide access to information, the role of library specialists in popularizing and disseminating reliable information is extremely important. They help users separate fact from myth, identify misinformation, and provide access to authoritative sources.

3. Development of information skills. Library professionals not only provide access to information, but also educate users to effectively search, evaluate, and use diverse resources. This is extremely important for digital literacy in the information society.

4. Development of reading culture. In the context of rapid information security, the culture of reading is undergoing changes. Library professionals contribute to the development of this culture by helping to select the most valuable from texts and developing critical thinking skills.

5. Promotion of scientific research. Library specialists play an important role in supporting scientific research by providing access to relevant information resources. Librarians are at the forefront of supporting researchers and facilitating their access to information. They help researchers find the necessary materials and sources for their work.

6. Cultural development. Libraries are centers of cultural life, where lectures, literary events, exhibitions, and other cultural events are held. Library specialists contribute to the development of cultural values and the expansion of the cultural horizons of users.

7. Preservation of cultural heritage. Libraries play an important role in preserving cultural heritage and archives. Library professionals help preserve and digitize valuable documents, ensuring their availability for future generations.

The listed aspects show how important the role of library specialists is in the modern information society. They are responsible for providing access to quality information, developing information skills, and supporting the cultural and scientific development of society.

An analysis of the market for the provision of educational services for the training of future library specialists showed that currently more than fifty institutions of higher education in Ukraine train specialists in the specialty 029 «Information, library and archival affairs».

Vasyl' Stus Donetsk National University (Vasyl' Stus Donetsk National University, 2023) is one of a number of institutions of higher education in Ukraine that train specialists in the socio-cultural and information spheres, as well as future library specialists. It should be noted that Vasyl' Stus DonNU has been a displaced university since 2014 due to the armed aggression of the Russian Federation. The educational institution actually started building its activities in the Vinnytsia region from scratch, because after moving to Vinnytsia, the university faced a number of problems, including a lack of necessary infrastructure for educational activities, insufficient premises and classrooms for conducting classes, a lack of technical resources and equipment, network infrastructure, no internet connection, etc.

During the years of exile, the Vasyl' Stus Donetsk National University:

- gradually restored the material and technical base, which allows for the educational process and scientific activity to be carried out today;
- preserved and qualitatively improved the teaching staff;
- began to restore positions lost due to relocation in national and international rankings;

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- took and steadily occupies a leading position among local competitors;
- created an unprecedented for the region network of partnerships and a new quality of relations between the higher school, the authorities, and the community for the implementation of joint socially useful projects and affairs.

Today, Vasyl' Stus DonNU is not only the only classical university in the Vinnytsia region, but it is also a powerful educational center of the Central Ukrainian region, a reliable partner for scientific and educational institutions, government, community and business, a comfortable environment for development, life, study, work (Vasyl' Stus Donetsk National University, 2023).

The Department of Management Information Systems (MIS) of the Faculty of Information and Applied Technologies of Vasyl' Stus DonNU trains future specialists in information, library and archival affairs. The department is a graduation for students of specialty 029 «Information, library and archival affairs».

After graduation, graduates of the Department of ISU have a formed set of knowledge, abilities, and skills that allow them to work in various organizations, enterprises, and institutions, including libraries.

Education takes place at two levels of education – bachelor's and master's (see Figure 1).

Fig. 1. Training of Specialists at the Department of Management Information Systems by Degrees and Levels of Education

Preparation for the bachelor's degree is carried out in accordance with the Educational Program «Documentation and information activities», upon completion of which graduates will receive the educational qualification of bachelor in information, library and archival affairs.

Educational Program meets the Standards of Higher Education of Ukraine: first (bachelor) level, the field of knowledge 02 Culture and art, specialty 029 «Information, library and archival affairs», which was approved and put into effect by the Order of the Ministry of Education and Science of Ukraine dated 12.12.2018 No. 1378 (Ministry of Education and Science of Ukraine, 2018).

An important focus of this Educational and Professional Program is its clear focus on thorough training in the possession and use of electronic processing and data visualization tools by students of higher education, provision of conditions for the formation and implementation of individual educational trajectories by applicants due to the variability of practice bases, subject areas of coursework and qualification work.

The goal of the Educational Program is the formation of a harmoniously developed personality, formation as an individual, a true patriot, and a qualified specialist in the field of information, library and archival affairs, capable of solving complex specialized tasks and practical problems in the field of information, library and archival affairs and realizing the value paradigm society that combines universal and national values, consolidates the Ukrainian nation and promotes Ukraine in the world as unbreakable, universal, invincible.

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Among the important goals of training under this Educational Program are: training specialists capable of solving complex specialized tasks and practical problems in the field of information, library and archival affairs.

Educational Program provides for the formation of competencies and program learning outcomes (see Figure 2).

Fig. 2. The Structure of Professional Training in Accordance with the Standard of Higher Education

The formation of integral competence is singled out as the ability of future specialists to solve complex specialized tasks and practical problems in the field of information, library and archival affairs or in the learning process, which involves the application of provisions and methods of information, library and archival affairs and is characterized by the complexity and uncertainty of conditions.

To work in library institutions, it is necessary to develop both general and special competencies that determine the ability to socialize, conduct professional and/or further educational activities. General competencies are important for the successful further professional and social activities of the acquirer and for his personal development. Among the general ones, we will single out the following: skills in using information and communication technologies; the ability to communicate in a foreign language; the ability to search, process, and analyze information from various sources, etc.

- Among the special competencies, the following are important:
 - Ability to select, analyze, evaluate, systematize, monitor, organize, store, distribute, and make available information and knowledge in any format.
 - Ability to use methods of systematization, search, storage, and classification of information for different types of content and media.
 - Ability to use modern applied computer technologies, software, network, and mobile technologies to solve specialty tasks.
 - The ability to analyze patterns of development, document-information flows, and arrays, as an artificially created subsystem of social communications.
 - Ability to maintain business communication with all subjects of the information market, users, partners, authorities and management, and mass media.

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- The ability to implement innovative technologies to produce information products and services, to improve the quality of information services for users of information, library and archive institutions.
 - Ability to design and create information systems, resources, products and services.
 - Ability to use PR and other applied social and communication technologies in the conditions of modern information technology infrastructure.
 - Ability to apply the principles of designing databases, information systems, social and other computer networks, electronic libraries, and archives.
 - Ability to use and improve automated information and search systems, organize electronic libraries and archives.
 - Ability to create, fill, and ensure the functioning of websites and web communities on the Internet.

The key trends of the educational process at the current stage are «usefulness and practicality» through research and real projects; «active learning», which includes a wide range of interactions between the teacher and the student – from discussing situational exercises in the classroom to interactive communication using the Internet; application of distance learning.

The department of MIS constantly carries out significant work on improving teaching methods: situational approach, simulation exercises, etc. Electronic summaries of lectures, practical tasks, methodical recommendations, and tasks for tests and exams have been developed for almost all disciplines.

Active methods are used in the learning process:

- game techniques — analysis of specific situations, simulation exercises, situational tasks, and business games;
- management pieces of training – the «brainstorming» method, questionnaires, testing.

Teaching methods of the group and individual creative search are carried out by applying situations or «cases». Students of higher education are offered a set of situations that differ in volume, structure of the proposed material, degree of saturation of information, nature of presentation of problems, and degree of uncertainty of the solution, which allows them to formulate different goals of «cases»: to teach students to «sort» information to solve a given problem, to navigate in risk conditions, identify key problems, form action programs.

As a result, the use of interactive technologies, problem-based learning, game technologies, and the case method in the educational process provides an opportunity to effectively achieve the main goal of training future specialists in the specialty 029 «Information, library and archival affairs» defined by the state standards of higher education, who are able to solve complex problems specialized tasks and practical problems in the field of information, library and archival affairs.

Graduates with a Bachelor's degree can continue their studies at the master's degree and obtain the Master's degree in information, library and archival affairs. Training is conducted in accordance with the Educational Program «Documentation and information support of management activities», which was developed in accordance with the Standard of Higher Education of Ukraine: second (master's) level, field of knowledge 02 Culture and art, specialty 029 «Information, library and archival affairs», which was approved and put into effect by the order of the Ministry of Education and Science of Ukraine dated May 24. No. 728 of 2019.

The purpose of this Educational Program is the formation of highly qualified specialists in the field of information, library and archival affairs, who are able to provide documentation and information support for management activities and to be aware of the value paradigm of society,

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which combines universal and national values, consolidates the Ukrainian nation and promotes Ukraine in the world as an indomitable, cathedral, invincible.

Analyzing educational programs in specialty 029 «Information, library and archival affairs», we note that each of them is unique. Uniqueness primarily depends on the strategy of the institution of higher education, which has a set of different types of resources. The uniqueness of this Educational Program at Vasyl' Stus DonNU is evidenced by additional features that distinguish it from other similar programs:

- possession and use by students of higher education of information management technologies, in particular documented information.
- formation and forecasting of options for operational and strategic management decisions;
- formation of skills and abilities in information confrontation and application of modern methods of protection of management information in computer systems and networks;
- use of information and search systems by students of higher education and promotion of information resources on the Internet.

The MIS department uses modern approaches to teaching and learning, namely: student-centered, problem-oriented, practice-oriented teaching and learning with mandatory elements of self-study, which allow students to develop important competencies. Among the general competencies of this Educational Program, we highlight the following:

- Ability to abstract thinking, analysis, and synthesis.
- Ability to generate new ideas (creativity).
- Ability to identify, pose, and solve problems.
- Ability to motivate people and move towards a common goal.
- Ability to make informed decisions.
- Ability to search, process, and analyze information from various sources.

The formation of special (professional, subject) competencies is important for successful professional realization and/or further educational activities in a specialty, including:

- Ability to form an effective management system for information, library and archival activities.
- The ability to organize work and manage information and analytical structural units at enterprises, organizations and institutions, in particular in archival and library ones.
- Ability to apply technologies and procedures of analytical and synthetic processing of scientific and management information.
- Ability to track development trends in the subject area by analyzing information flows and arrays.
- Ability to apply computer technologies in order to improve professional activity and understand the principles of designing and functioning of automated databases, semantic web, web services, and social media.
- Ability to use knowledge of scientific principles and methods of archival and library science, strategies, models, standards, and methods of development and administration of library and archive systems in professional activities.

Teaching is carried out in the form of traditional and interactive lectures, laboratory work, seminars, practical classes using the method of small groups, individual classes, practice sessions, consultations with teachers, business games, and e-learning using specialized electronic tools: Moodle system, Microsoft Teams applications, Microsoft SharePoint, etc.

At Vasyl' Stus DonNU, students of higher education are provided with the formation of an individual educational trajectory through a free choice of academic disciplines. In particular, an

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individual educational trajectory can be implemented by choosing a specific certificate program introduced at the university, and you can also choose disciplines from other educational programs, a list (course catalog), taking into account your own needs and interests in future professional activity.

Considering the requirements of the information society, special attention is paid to the information component in the process of training at both the bachelor's and master's levels. In the structure of the formation of professional competencies of future specialists, informational competence occupies an important place, the mastery of which means a qualitatively new level in their professional training and further professional development. There is a belief that graduates of specialty 029 «Information, library and archival affairs» are, first of all, information workers who know how to work with information – collect, process, create, store, and distribute, using modern digital technologies.

The professional training of future specialists should provide not only high-quality theoretical training but thorough practical training, which is an integral part of the educational process and because of which a direct connection between theoretical training and the acquisition of practical skills by higher education students is realized. It is important to note that the bases of practical training for candidates of the department, among other enterprises and organizations, are public, special libraries of the city of Vinnytsia, such as: V. Otamanovsky Vinnytsia Regional Universal Scientific Library, Scientific Library of the National Pirogov Memorial Medical University, Vinnytsia etc.

In terms of transparency and availability for review, educational programs are published on the official website of the university in full in free access for all interested parties: educational institutions, graduates, and stakeholders. Educational programs are constantly being improved, in particular, regarding their content, the list of educational components, their volumes, etc. Students of higher education, graduates, and stakeholders are involved in the improvement (<https://fiat.donnu.edu.ua/kafedra-isu-2/#os>).

Graduates of the department have a high level of professional knowledge aimed at their implementation in library institutions. Thus, graduates of the Department of MIS work in various libraries of the city, such as V. Otamanovsky Vinnytsia Regional Universal Scientific Library, Scientific Library of Vinnytsia National Technical University, Institute of Culture «Vinnytsia City Centralized Library System» etc.

It is important to note that during 2022-2023 Vasyli' Stus Donetsk National University successfully passed all stages of the accreditation procedure of educational and professional programs at the first (bachelor) and second (master) levels and received Certificates of accreditation of the National Agency for Quality Assurance of Higher Education for a period of 5 years, which confirms the high-quality training of students of higher education.

In the context of the internationalization of higher library and information education in Ukraine, it is important to study the experience of training future library specialists abroad to determine directions for improving domestic educational programs. It should be noted that European systems for training librarians with higher qualifications have some common and distinctive features, depending on the higher education system of an individual country.

For example, the integration model of higher library and information education in France has a complex and multi-level organizational structure. Education in French higher education institutions is organized in three stages - cycles. The first lasts two years, during which 54% of the entire contingent of university students acquires a general higher education, refines professional orientation, and receives the first academic qualification (intermediate DEUG diploma). The second cycle is a cycle of deepening and professional training (2–3 years) and is divided into two

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stages with the provision of *licence* and *maîtrise*. The third cycle is specialized and prepares for the start of serious scientific research. Admission to it is by competition, and the duration of study is one year. That is, after general scientific studies at the college, which is a mandatory condition for obtaining a full higher education, the applicant studies for 2 years and receives a bachelor's degree. The next year of study gives French students the opportunity to obtain a licentiate degree. Master's programs are designed for one year of study.

Currently, of the country's 45 universities that train information specialists, most offer educational programs that are integrated in the content. Documentary librarians are trained not only in specialized institutions of higher education, such as the National Institute of Documentation Technologies, but also in the departments of information and communication studies of humanities faculties of classical universities (Sorbonne University, Paul Valéry University, and others), in branch institutes (technological, economic, political research and others). A flexible system of higher education enables students to implement an individual learning trajectory and alternate it with practical activities after obtaining a certain educational level (Humenchuk, 2022).

For example, the National School of Libraries and Information (Enssib), an associate member of the University of Lyon, trains information, documentation, and library science managers for the public and private sectors through a combination of initial and continuing education. The work and study program is fully integrated into the Enssib pedagogical model, where practical experience and academic knowledge interact and complement each other. This teaching method is also in line with the school's ongoing concern to offer the best professional integration for students.

Based on a bachelor's degree, students can obtain a double master's degree in two years of study: a master's degree in information and library sciences and a master's degree in the field of digital humanities.

In the first year of study, students form a theoretical base in the field of library science, information, and documentation, and in the second year, they deepen their professional specialization, choosing to study in one of the following educational master's programs:

- Master 2 Digital Archives (ARN)
- Master 2 Library and Documentation Policy (PBD)
- Master 2 Scientific and Technical Information (SIBIST) (Enssib, n.d.).

A mandatory component of the professional training of masters in information and library sciences at this educational institution is practical training aimed at in-depth professional integration of education seekers, immersion in the professional environment. In addition to working in a certain document and communication institution according to the study profile (publishing house, archive, library, documentation service), students have the opportunity to undergo a long-term internship (from 4 to 6 months) in university libraries, business structures, specialized documentation centers of European countries, Canada, USA. This allows you to gain professional experience and significantly increases the employment opportunities for school graduates.

Conclusions

Therefore, in the context of the growing influence of digital technologies and wide access to knowledge, the issue of professional training of future specialists in the library field becomes especially relevant. Specialists in the library sphere in the information society are becoming key actors in providing quality information, developing cultural values and skills necessary for digital literacy in the information environment. They act not only as intermediaries in access to knowledge

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but also as mentors who teach how to search, analyze, and use information effectively. Therefore, the professional training of future specialists in the library field must consider modern trends and requirements of the information society. Information skills, critical thinking, the ability to work with various sources and technologies are the key components that will help library professionals respond to modern challenges.

Library education and professional training of future specialists of library institutions is an important component in the context of the modern digital transformations of society. Effective professional training of future specialists in the library field is of decisive importance for the development of the information society and for ensuring quality access to knowledge and cultural heritage. An integral part of this process is the promotion of innovation, the development of creative approaches, and the formation of critical thinking, competent, and responsible specialists who can meet the challenges of the information society.

In this context, it is important to improve educational programs aimed at training library specialists, considering the interdisciplinary nature of the information environment.

The study of foreign experience of the best practices of training future specialists in the information and library sphere provides an opportunity to identify the features of similar foreign programs, with the aim of introducing them into the system of training specialists in the library sphere of Ukraine. Thus, double degree programs with opportunistic specializations that are in demand on the country's information market, in-depth practical training of future specialists in document and information institutions, the possibility of dual education at the master's level, international mobility of students - all this is useful for borrowing by the Ukrainian system training of library and information specialists in specialty 029 "Information, library, and archival affairs".

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Професійна підготовка майбутніх фахівців бібліотечної сфери у Донецькому національному університеті імені Василя Стуса

Мета дослідження – репрезентація досвіду та напрямів професійної підготовки майбутніх фахівців бібліотек у закладі вищої освіти, що базується на інтеграції освіти, сучасних інформаційно-комунікаційних технологій та практичної складової, дає змогу професійної реалізації фахівців в сучасних бібліотечних установах відповідно до вимог інформаційного суспільства. **Методика.** У дослідженні використано комплекс загальних та спеціальних методів наукового пізнання, а саме: метод аналізу документів шляхом вивчення та представлення освітніх програм підготовки майбутніх фахівців щодо їх відповідності потребам ринку праці; метод спостереження за процесом підготовки здобувачів у закладі вищої освіти, його особливостей та адаптації до вимог інформаційного суспільства; описовий метод та метод логічного викладу результатів дослідження. **Результати** показали, що організація професійної підготовки, стратегії навчання, які застосовуються у Донецькому національному університеті імені Василя Стуса на кафедрі інформаційних систем управління сприяють успішній професійній реалізації майбутніх фахівців бібліотек відповідно до вимог сьогодення. Випускники кафедри є висококваліфікованими та конкурентоздатними фахівцями на ринку праці. У **висновках** аргументовано актуальність професійної підготовки майбутніх фахівців бібліотечної сфери в контексті цифрових трансформацій суспільства. Наголошено на важливості вдосконалення навчальних програм, спрямованих на підготовку фахівців бібліотечної сфери.

Keywords: інформаційне суспільство; бібліотека; бібліотечний працівник; Донецький національний університет імені Василя Стуса; професійна підготовка

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